

ACTIVELY COOLED BATTERY PACKAGING USING VASCULAR COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Battery-powered electric vehicles have seen increased use in recent years due to advances in battery technology and a societal desire to move away from fossil fuels. A unique challenge for the design of these vehicles is packaging the hundreds or even thousands of batteries present in the vehicle. First, the packaging must protect batteries from damage during rough driving conditions or collisions. This is a major safety issue since damaged batteries can develop short circuits that lead to cell overheating, thermal runaway, and fire [1]. Second, the packaging system must provide thermal management since most batteries used in electric vehicles (such as lithium-ion batteries) have poor cycling performance at both high and low temperature extremes [2]. The two main challenges for lithium-ion batteries are how to keep the overall battery temperature low during discharge and how to prevent temperature gradients from developing across individual battery cells.

An example packaging scheme is that of the Chevy Volt, which has 288 lithium-ion pouch cells stacked in a T-shaped array (see Fig. 1) [3]. There are 144 aluminum fins located between the cells through which a coolant is pumped for thermal management. The battery cells and cooling fins are surrounded by glass-reinforced nylon cases, the cases are bound together with steel end plates, and finally the entire assembly is surrounded by steel for added protection. As a whole, the packaging is quite complex and accounts for about half of the weight of the battery assembly.

Here we propose a novel packaging scheme that uses microvascular fiber-reinforced composites. Batteries will be embedded within structural composites that contain channels near the battery surface for coolant flow (see Fig. 2). The channels will be formed in the composites using a recently developed technique where sacrificial polylactide (PLA) fibers are incorporated into a composite and vaporized after cure [4]. The resulting packaging will possess the high strength, high stiffness, and low weight characteristic of fiber-reinforced composites while housing a seamlessly integrated thermal management network.

To assist in material selection and channel design for this packaging scheme, simulations were run in ANSYS Fluent to show the response of a single composite cooling fin to a battery-generated heat flux. Fins were simulated with different material properties, different numbers of channels, and with both parallel and counter coolant flow. In the near future, these simulation results will be verified experimentally by fabricating microvascular composites and testing their cooling performance using an infrared (IR) camera setup. This study thus serves to complement both simulations [5 – 7] and experiments [8 – 9] on battery cooling.

2 Methods

2.1 Simulation Setup

The simulation setup is shown schematically in Fig. 3. A single composite fin is subject to a heat flux on both sides, representing the heat flux that would be provided by surrounding batteries during vehicle operation. A constant total flow rate of coolant of 56

mL/min passes through straight channels evenly spaced along the height of the fin; four channel designs were simulated consisting of 6, 8, 12, or 16 channels. Coolant flow is either parallel (all channels have flow in the same direction) or counter flow (coolant flows in alternating directions from channel to channel). The fin dimensions, coolant and fin material properties, and boundary conditions are provided in Table 1. The spacings between channels in the fins are given in Table 2; the channels are centered in the thickness of the fin and are spaced evenly throughout the height.

This simulation setup is partially inspired by simulations on aluminum cooling fins performed by Jarrett and Kim [6] who based their work on information provided by GM Canada. Their simulated fins were 160 mm wide x 200 mm high to match the size of a battery cell and 1 mm thick. A heat flux of 500 W/m^2 was applied to both sides; this flux represents an average value of heat given off by a single pouch cell battery during vehicle operation. Cooling was provided a 50/50 water-ethylene glycol coolant pumped at a constant flow rate of 0.001 kg/s (56 mL/min) and an inlet temperature of $27 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

For our simulations, the fin width and height are preserved from Jarrett and Kim. The fin thickness is set to 3 mm, a value that gives the current scheme the same volume of packaging per battery to that used in the Volt system. The coolant material properties are also preserved from Jarrett and Kim. Note that the coolant viscosity and specific heat are simulated with temperature-dependency.

Two different composite materials are simulated for the fins: pitch-based carbon fibers (Nippon CN80 fabric) in an epoxy matrix (EPON 862 / EPIKURE W) and PAN-based carbon fibers (Toray T300 fabric) in an epoxy matrix (EPON 862 / EPIKURE W). It is desirable to simulate both materials since pitch-based carbon fiber has much higher thermal conductivity than PAN-based carbon fiber, which is desirable for cooling applications. Pitch-based fiber is also substantially more expensive than PAN-based fiber, however.

The material properties for these composites, given in Table 3, are estimates made for biaxial composites with a 60% volume fraction of fibers.

Density values were calculated using manufacturer information for the fibers and matrix. Heat capacity values were calculated using manufacturer information for the resin and PAN-based fabric and a value for the heat capacity of pitch fabric from Always-Cooper et al. [10]. In-plane thermal conductivity for the composites was calculated using the rule of mixtures, with the fiber thermal conductivity from manufacturer information and the resin thermal conductivity from Ganguli et al. [11]. Transverse conductivity for the pitch composite was taken from Sharp et al. [12] and transverse conductivity for the PAN composite was taken from Rolfes and Hammerschmidt [13].

For boundary conditions, the coolant flow rate and inlet temperature are preserved from Jarrett and Kim. The heat flux from each side of 500 W/m^2 is also preserved. It is worth noting, however, that Jarrett and Kim simulated the cooling scheme in Fig. 1 where there are two batteries per cooling fin while there is only one battery per cooling fin in the proposed packaging scheme (Fig. 2). Thus, each fin in the proposed scheme is only subject to half of a battery-generated heat flux on each side. Maintaining the full 500 W/m^2 heat flux from each side in the current simulations thus represents an extreme case where each battery is generating twice its average heat flux. This case is used to determine if the composite fins can survive extreme operating conditions. The goal is for the fins to maintain a maximum surface temperature T_{max} under $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under these conditions while having minimal values of average surface temperature T_{av} and the standard deviation of temperature across the fin surface σ_T .

2.2 Mesh Generation and Simulation in Fluent

Finite volume meshes were created using the commercial program ANSYS Meshing. Meshes used for data analysis contained between 1.41 million elements (0.24 million in the fluid domain) for the six-channel fin and 2.81 million elements (0.59 million in the fluid domain) for the 16-channel fin. Sweep meshing with a sweep size of 160 elements was used along the width of the fin, meaning that the mesh was evenly divided into 160 columns of elements along the width. A fluid face sizing of 0.04 mm was used at the channel inlets and a solid face sizing of 0.375 mm was used for the solid face surrounding the channel inlets. A growth

rate of 1.035 was used. The choice of these meshing parameters is discussed in section 2.3 on mesh convergence below.

Steady-state simulations in the commercial program ANSYS Fluent were run using the SIMPLE pressure-velocity scheme, Green-Gauss node based gradient discretization, second order pressure discretization, third order MUSCL momentum discretization, and third order MUSCL energy discretization. Simulations were conducted for all combinations of the four channel designs (6-channel, 8-channel, 12-channel, and 16-channel), composite material (pitch-based vs. PAN-based), and parallel vs. counter flow. Convergence was defined as when the energy residual reduced to 10^{-6} and all other residuals reduced to 10^{-3} . Values of maximum temperature T_{max} , average temperature T_{av} , and standard deviation of temperature σ_T were extracted for each simulation case.

2.3 Mesh Convergence Study

To ensure that meshes of adequate size were used for the simulations, a convergence study was conducted with the 6-channel, PAN-based, parallel flow fin. Mesh size was controlled with a fluid face sizing at the channel inlets, a solid face sizing for the solid face surrounding the inlets, and a sweep size. First, meshes with a solid face sizing of 0.5 mm and a sweep size of 160 elements were constructed with various fluid face sizings to generate different numbers of fluid elements per mesh. As shown in Fig. 4, the value of T_{av} increases with increasing number of fluid elements and then plateaus. A face sizing of 0.04 mm, corresponding to 0.24×10^6 fluid elements, was chosen for future use.

The sweep size was then modified for meshes with a 0.04 mm fluid face sizing and a solid face sizing of 0.5 mm. Increasing the sweep size results in an increasing number of both fluid and solid elements. Sweep size had little effect on T_{max} or T_{av} amongst the different meshes but σ_T was seen to increase with increasing sweep size and then plateau off (Fig. 5). A sweep size of 160, corresponding to 1.34×10^6 total elements, was chosen for meshing. Finally, the solid face sizing was varied, which impacts the number of solid elements in the mesh. The influence of the solid face sizing on the results was minimal and a final value of 0.375 mm was chosen. The final

mesh for the 6-channel case had 1.41×10^6 elements. All other meshes used these three optimal mesh parameters.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Effect of Carbon Fiber Material

Fig. 6 shows the temperature distributions obtained for the 6-channel pitch-based and PAN-based fins with parallel flow. Temperatures are shown both at the midplane and at the surface of each fin. For both the pitch-based and PAN-based fins, the middle of the fin and the surface of the fin have similar temperature distributions within the solid domain, with the maximum temperature of the fin surface being within 1 °C of the maximum temperature in the middle of the fin. The relative insignificance of through-thickness temperature gradients compared to in-plane temperature gradients can be attributed to the thinness of the fins compared to their planar dimensions. Proper material selection for the fins will thus be dictated largely by in-plane thermal conductivity, not transverse thermal conductivity.

As seen in Figs. 6a and 6b, the pitch-based fin has a gradually rising temperature from left to right, mirroring the temperature rise of the coolant as it flows from left to right in the fin. The maximum temperature of the fin, 42 °C, is within 6 °C of the average fluid outlet temperature and is close to the goal of $T_{max} < 40$ °C. In contrast, the PAN-based fin (Figs. 6c and 6d) has a temperature distribution largely marked by ‘hot spots’ in between the channels. The maximum temperature of the fin, 61 °C, is far above the target value. The PAN-based fin also has a much higher T_{av} and σ_T as compared to the pitch-based fin. Specific values of T_{max} , T_{av} , and σ_T for these and all other simulation cases are given in Figs. 7 – 9.

The better performance of the pitch-based fins is expected based on their higher in-plane thermal conductivity ($96 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) as compared to PAN-based fins ($3.3 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$). This higher conductivity stops temperature gradients from forming between channels.

3.2 Effect of Counter vs. Parallel Flow

Fig. 10 shows the temperature distributions obtained for the 6-channel pitch-based and PAN-based fins with counter flow. As seen in Fig. 10a, the use of counter flow in the pitch fin greatly reduces temperature variation across the fin as compared to parallel flow (Fig. 6b). This is observed as an approximately threefold decrease in σ_T from the parallel flow case to the counter flow case. The improved performance of counter flow in this regard is expected since cold inlet fluid is now divided between the left and right sides of the fin instead of being confined to a single side. The T_{max} of the counter flow fin is also less than that from parallel flow, dropping below the target of 40 °C. The 6-channel, pitch-based, counter flow fin thus meets the success criteria for this study.

For the PAN-based fin, the use of counter flow also drops σ_T and T_{max} . However, as seen in Fig. 10b, the fin still has significant hot spots that develop between channels. The T_{max} value for the counter flow fin, 57 °C, is still well above the target value.

Interestingly, counter flow produces higher values of T_{av} as compared to parallel flow, with the effect being most pronounced for pitch-based fins with a large number of channels. This could be explained by the fact that parallel flow provides a locally cool region near all of the channel inlets which lowers the average temperature of the fin as a whole.

3.3 Effect of Number of Channels

Increasing the number of channels in a fin, while still maintaining the same total coolant flow rate, leads to smaller temperature gradients developing in the fin since there are smaller spaces between channels. This effect is most prominently seen in the PAN-based fins; as shown in Figs. 7 - 9, T_{max} , T_{av} , and σ_T all significantly decrease for PAN-based fins with an increasing number of channels.

An example of these changes is seen by comparing the temperature distributions in 16-channel PAN-based fins, shown in Fig. 11, to the distributions in six-channel fins shown in Fig 6d and Fig. 10b. The 16-channel, parallel flow fin has a temperature distribution similar to the six-channel pitch-based fin (Fig. 6b) and has a similar T_{max} of 42 °C. The use of

counter flow results in even smaller temperature gradients forming and gives a T_{max} just under the target of 40 °C. The 16-channel, counter flow fin thus matches the success criteria, showing that PAN-based fins can obtain adequate cooling performance if they possess enough channels.

Pitch-based fins also see a reduction in T_{max} and T_{av} with more channels, although the effect is less pronounced. The value of σ_T shows no clear trend with an increasing number of channels; this implies that σ_T has reached a plateau value for the pitch-based fins, with deviations eventually expected at channel numbers less than six. It is worth noting that, at high channel number, PAN-based counter flow fins actually have lower σ_T values than pitch-based parallel flow fins. This shows that the use of counter flow can sometimes be a more significant variable than the thermal conductivity of a fin in preventing temperature deviations in a fin.

In summary, T_{max} , T_{av} , and σ_T for the simulated fins are seen to all be functions of fin material properties, the use of counter vs. parallel flow, and the number of channels in each fin. Pitch-based fins outperform PAN-based fins due to higher thermal conductivity, but the addition of more channels allows for PAN-based fins to compete with pitch-based ones. This is demonstrated by the fact that obtaining a T_{max} less than 40 °C can be accomplished with either a six-channel pitch-based fin or a 16-channel PAN-based fin. Finally, the use of counter flow is seen to significantly lower temperature deviations in the fin as reflected by lower values of σ_T . Counter flow also provides the tradeoff of slightly lower T_{max} values and slightly higher T_{av} values.

4 Conclusions

Actively cooled composite battery packaging would enable lightweight protection of batteries while maintaining optimal operating temperature. To demonstrate the feasibility of using carbon fiber composites for battery cooling, simulations were run for both pitch-based and PAN-based composites with varying numbers of channels and with both parallel and counter flow. Adequate cooling performance was demonstrated for both materials, with PAN-based fins requiring more channels than pitch-based fins to offset their lower thermal

conductivity. It was also seen that counter flow is generally preferred over parallel flow since it provides smaller temperature deviations across the fins and smaller maximum temperatures.

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Fig. 1. Battery packaging for the 288 pouch cells in the Chevrolet Volt. Image from reference [3].

Fig. 2. Schematic of battery packaging using actively cooled microvascular composites.

Fig. 3. Schematic of Fluent cooling simulations. Dimensions of fin are in mm.

Table 1. Parameters used in Fluent simulations.

Property	Value
<u>Dimensions</u>	
Plate width (mm)	160
Plate height (mm)	200
Plate thickness (mm)	3
Channel diameter (mm)	0.5
<u>Coolant fluid</u>	
	50/50 water-ethylene glycol
Density (kg m^{-3})	1065
Viscosity ^a (Pa s)	0.00315
Specific heat ^a ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	3494
Thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	0.419
<u>Plate materials</u>	
<u>Pitch-based carbon fiber</u>	
Density (kg m^{-3})	1780
Specific heat ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	950
In-plane thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	96
Transverse thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	1.0
<u>PAN-based carbon fiber</u>	
Density (kg m^{-3})	1540
Specific heat ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	1000
In-plane thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	3.3
Transverse thermal conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	0.71
<u>Boundary conditions</u>	
Total coolant flow rate (kg s^{-1})	0.001
Coolant inlet temperature (K)	300
Coolant outlet pressure (Pa)	0
Heat flux on each side (W m^{-2})	500

^aProperty stated at 300 K

Table 2. Channel spacings along the height of the cooling fins for different simulation cases.

Simulation case	Distance from plate edge to center of outermost channel (mm)	Distance between center of adjacent channels (mm)
6-channel	13.0	34.8
8-channel	12.5	25.0
12-channel	6.5	17.0
16-channel	5.5	12.6

Fig. 4. Mesh convergence plot of T_{av} for the 6-channel, PAN-based, parallel flow fin.

Fig. 5. Mesh convergence plot of σ_T for the 6-channel, PAN-based, parallel flow fin.

Fig. 6. Steady-state temperature distributions of 6-channel fins with parallel flow. Coolant flow is from left to right.

Fig. 7. Maximum surface temperature vs. the number of microchannels

Fig. 9. Standard deviation of surface temperature vs. the number of microchannels

Fig. 8. Average surface temperature vs. number of microchannels

Fig. 10. Steady-state temperature distributions of 6-channel fins with counter flow. Arrows indicate locations of coolant entry.

Fig. 11. Steady-state temperature distributions of 16-channel PAN-based fins with parallel and counter coolant flow.